

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING NEWSPAPER CLICHES AND PHRASES

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Annotation: *This article discusses phrases and clichés in newspapers and magazines. Experiences and innovative methods of learning and teaching these phrases and clichés in newspapers are given attention. An example of the opinions of linguistics who thought about these methods and directions is given.*

Key words: *cliches, phrases, approaches, lexical competence.*

In the process of learning and teaching English as a foreign language, that is, when the skill of learning a new foreign language is being formed, any method contributes to an effective result. Reading and analyzing newspapers and magazines allows me to develop new language integration skills as well as keeping up with the times and being aware of new phrases and clichés.

But learning phrases and clichés from newspapers and magazines has its own steps. If we consider 11-15 years old as the early age of magazine reading, this period can be compared to the first stage of increasing lexical competence. In this period, it is better to start with short advertisements in magazines and newspapers, pictorial texts, cartoons, comics and sports news. At the next stage, there are relatively no obstacles and difficulties in reading and analyzing political news and artistic-journalistic works. Each linguist or language teacher has his own approach to this issue. For example, according to Martin Sketchley, there are five ways to use newspapers in the EFL classroom.

“One way to incorporate authentic text in the EFL classroom is to use Newspapers with students. Furthermore, should teachers be located in a country where English newspapers are limited, then the internet is also available to access newspaper articles. However, the issue for many teachers is how they should use newspaper articles in the classroom so that it is accessible and comprehensible for learners.

1. What's The Story

- Before the start of the lesson, find images from newspapers or popular news websites. Print them out and laminate them if you wish.
- Stick them up around the classroom and get turner to wander around, looking at the images for a few minutes.
- Once students have finished walking around the classroom, students then are paired up or placed into small groups. They discuss what they already know about the news stories from the images and share their ideas together.
- Elicit possible news stories from the learners and then once you have boarded up their ideas, tell them that you will give them the news articles. They must match the images to the article that they read.
- Once all students have matched their article to the image, they could share something new that they had learnt from it.
- You could extend the activity with idea number five below.

2. Guess The Article

- Select an interesting or odd news article for this activity, preferably an article which is engaging.
- Write up eight key words from the article and tell learners that they need to predict the story.
- Put students into small groups of three or four.
- Student present to the class and then you provide feedback and correction where necessary.
- Once finished, students compare their own stories to the original news article.

3. Matching Headlines, Images & Articles

- Newspaper articles, particularly those online, have an image included with it. To combine all elements of a news article, teachers could use the headline, image and article to make an engaging and rewarding activity.
- Choose between three and four news articles. Cut up the headlines, images and text and laminate them.
- Place students into small groups: one group with just the headlines, one group with images and the other group with just the main text.
- For students with headlines, they must think about the story and a possible image that they could draw. The group with an image of the article should think of a headline and a possible story for it. The final group of students with the article could think of a headline or a corresponding image to go with it.
- Once students have finished and you have helped where necessary, tell students that they must check their ideas by matching headlines, images and articles together.

4. Headline Extensions

- Tell students that you are going to distribute different headlines to each small group of learners and they must work together to expand the news article just from the headline.
- Write up “*Trump Meets Queen*” and elicit possible meanings, asking learners to write a full sentence. Board up something along the lines of “*Donald Trump met the Queen*”.
- Now write up “*Trump To Meet Queen*” and ask what the difference is. Elicit that the tense refers to the future in this form. Ask students to write up the whole sentence on the whiteboard: “*Donald Trump is going to meet the Queen*”.
- Hand out different headlines and ask students to write up full sentences from the headlines.
- Once you have elicited possible examples, and provided support where necessary, get students to complete the story as much as possible in small groups.
- Review the original story to the students’ examples and ask them to check to see how close their predictions were.

5. Student Questions

1. Give students a newspaper article to read in small groups or pairs.
2. Tell students that they are going to read the article in greater detail and create comprehension questions based upon the article.
3. Students could have different articles or the same article – it is up to you.
4. The small groups or pairs of students work together for a short period of time and they must make some comprehension questions. Normally, I set a minimum of 10 questions but you may increase or decrease this depending upon the size of the article.
5. Once students have made their corresponding questions, and have written them on a piece of paper, redistribute the questions and article to another group.
6. The other group must then answer the corresponding questions. “[5]

Paul Dixon and Robert Skole, authors of the first dictionary of journalistic expressions, make the following points; “We have a “Dictionary of Slang and Unconventional English”, a “Dictionary of Obsolete English”, a “Dictionary of Catch Phrases”, a “Dictionary of Confusable Words”, a “Dictionary of Epithets and Terms of Address”, a “Dictionary of Euphemisms”, and a “Dictionary of Sports Idioms”, but not one on *Journalese*; that is, until now. *Journalese*, for those not familiar with the term, is a code word for journalist jargon, distinguished by clichés, sensationalism, and triteness of thought, which usually appear in your local newspaper but is rarely spoken at the office water cooler.”[3]

And according to Christopher Taylor's thoughts and advises, "Newspaper articles are written by journalists and reporters to inform the public. News stories report on current events and are usually time-sensitive, so they are written soon after an incident or event has happened. You may analyze the language in newspapers as part of an assignment for a class or as a way to improve your own news-writing skills. Start by looking at the headline of the news article. You can then examine the body of the article to better understand newspaper language, focusing on structure, tense, voice, rhetoric, and tone. Part 1. Evaluating the Headline: Look for nouns and verbs in the headline, Check if the headline consists of a string of nouns, Notice if the headline has no articles like "a," "an," or "the", Look for verb changes in the headline, Check for wordplay in the headline, Look for alliteration. Ask "who," "what," "where," and "why" when reading the headline, Use the headline to understand the body of the article.

Part 2. Examining the Structure, Voice, and Tense of the Article: Identify where the article is located in the newspaper, Analyze the lede, or the first line, of the article, Look up unfamiliar words or phrases. Check for the active voice, Summarize the article in your own words.

Part 3. Looking at Rhetoric and Tone: Look for statements that show bias, Identify hyperbolic language, Look for clichés, Check for evidence or sources used to support an argument, Identify allusions in the article, Look for inclusive language, Determine the overall tone of the article. " [2]

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